

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIVEMENT

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

FOR ACTIVELY PARTICIPATING IN THE JOURNAL

Музаффарова Н.С

**ИБН СИНО ТАЪЛИМОТИДА ГАСТРОЭЗОФАГЕАЛ РЕФЛЮКС КАСАЛЛИГИ ҲАМДА МЕЪДА
КАСАЛЛИКЛАРИ ВА УНГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ЁНДАШИШ**

WILL BE AWARDED FOR THEIR PARTICIPATION IN THE ARTICLE

zenodo

2023/IYUN

